

Indian IT employees' performance depends upon their well-being at workplace-A study using Machine Learning tools.

Sasmita Senapati 1

Research Scholar, Department of Management, Biju Patanaik University of Technology
(BPUT)

Dr. Mousumi Panda 2

Professor, Centre for Agri Management, Utkal University

Dr. Bandita Dash 3

Assistant Professor

MBA, Gita Autonomous College, Bhubaneswar,

Dr. Bijayalaxmi Panda 4

Associate Professor

Department of Computer Science and Technology, Gita Autonomous College, Bhubaneswar
Odisha

Abstract:

Employee wellbeing refers to the overall holistic development of the workforce. The purpose of the paper is to establish the relationship between employee performance and employee wellbeing. Employee wellbeing, a new sustainable HR dimension which has gained momentum after covid-19 pandemic has various factors. Our analysis primarily emphasized machine learning-based feature importance and predictive modelling. The study focused on machine learning-based predictive modelling and feature importance analysis to identify different factors of employee well-being and its impact on employee performance. Using a descriptive research design and convenient data sampling of 205 no. of respondents, the researchers tried to find out the impact of employee well-being factors, those result in the happiness of employees ultimately resulting to enhanced performance. The findings of the study revealed surprising facts about the relationship

between well-being and performance. As work from home concept is rapidly adopted by IT companies, the researchers faced difficulty for a bigger no of sample size. The future scope of the study is to again establish a relationship between employees' well-being, employee performance and employees connect.

Keywords: Employee wellbeing, Employee Performance, Sustainable HR dimensions, predictive modelling.

Introduction:

In earlier researches it was found that employee's productivity and organization performance are positively connected to human resource management (HRM) (e.g. Combs *et al.* 2006). But these days only HRM is not sufficient enough to meet the growing demands and expectations. So now-a-days the focus has been tilted more towards employee centered HR policies which is sustainable HR policies (Boxall and Macky 2009; Guest 1997; Nishii and Wright 2008). It is not an easy task to have any concrete verdict by reviewing the literature on wellbeing and employee performance (Appelbaum 2002). So in order to fill up the gap and reach at a solid conclusion, a survey had conducted on different and leading educational organizations and corporate houses of India by analyzing different literatures concerning employee wellbeing. And the survey reveals that both Employee Performance & Organization Performance connected to the sustainable HR practice, i.e. employee wellbeing are certainly have a positive and optimized outcome can have mutual gains (e.g. Legge 1995; Ramsay *et al.* 2000)

In the last couple of years, the macro environments of business houses have witnessed a complete alteration. Because of rapid growth of worldwide rivalry of businesses, there are increasing demands for corporate financial result, profitability and shareholder value (Huselid 1995; Becker et al. 2001; Boselie et al. 2005). It is seen that there have been dual impact of the reorganizing and scaling down the business because of more rigorous labour practice. Dual impact like positive effect on profitability but a negative one on employees' well-being and workability (Vahtera et al. 1997; McDonough 2000; Dunham 2001). So these days corporate professionals (more specifically HRs) and academicians have universally incorporated their roles in widening company performance.

Employee wellbeing is a term which means the overall (both physical and mental) wellbeing of employees and includes many different ingredients such as job satisfaction, anxiety, burnout (Warr 1990, Ryff/Keyes 1995; Daniels 2000; Holman 2002). These different areas are being identified by the researchers and also included in the present study.

The focus area of writing this paper is double folded. First is to find out whether the above-mentioned sectors are implementing any well-being practices as new dimension of Sustainable HRM. And second is to analyze any possible connection between employee wellbeing and

Employee Performance & Organization Performance. The study has conducted by taking data from the IT sector professional. A systematic and empirical data analysis has been done in order to establish the relationship between employee well-being and Employee Performance.

Previous researches show that not many employee well-being practices are adopted in any sectors in India. Some of the sectors are even deprived of being provided the basic minimum needs which in turn they had a negative attitude towards the work and the environment that they work. This eventually hampered their work and overall Employee Performance get negatively affected. Looking at the gravity of the situation and knowing this now-a-days these sectors have adopted and started implementing some well-being activities and to their surprise the result is pretty good.

Literature Review:

Contrast to earlier times we now are living in a much more improved world and to a very greater degree is inclined by the knowledge economy because of better educational system. This knowledge economy is always in search of good, talented candidates possessing specialized skills and knowledge which make their USP and is difficult to replace those (Hellgren et al., 2008). The employees know that this is the world of cut-throat competition and they need to be very competitive in their respective position and it is very important also to infuse and retain those talented candidates for organizational success.

A normal human being contributes twenty five percent of the adult life towards his/her profession(s). A person needs to feel and experience good at his/her own profession and good work must be the pivotal ingredient in a person's overall wellbeing as he/she is connected with it very deeply. So, experience whether it is good or bad must come from the organization he/she is associated with. Generally, if the organization is good and having good employee wellbeing practices and positive organizational attitude, an employee feels high level of satisfaction. High level of satisfaction is connected to superior work performance (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005), low turnover intentions, low actual turnover (Boehm and Lyubomirsky, 2008), greater effort and thought put into work, less absenteeism and fewer work-related injuries (Keyes and Grzywacz, 2005). These practices affect well-being which is very significant in achieving organizational success. Thus, the organizations must support and implement employee wellbeing practices (Dewe and Cooper, 2012; Hone et al., 2015).

Before the connection between employee wellbeing and Employee Performance is measured, we should first know that why employee wellbeing can affect Employee Performance. In this regard so many literatures have been studied and it came to known that most famous and a century old theory is the Human Relations Theory. According to this theory employee wellbeing is assessed in different areas like job satisfaction, job morale which leads to higher productivity higher (see Strauss (1968). According to the theory it is clearly known that positivity begets positivity like attitudes towards life can bring healthy behavioural implications (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975).

Employees generally do not remain absent from the work place those who have a positive mind set and turnover ratio is very less.

In the context of employee wellbeing (EWB) and Employee Performance the role of leadership based on morality is very much significant (Sarwar et al, 2020). In this area lot many research works also have conducted to know the effects of employee wellbeing and Employee Performance (Cheng et al., 2014; Schaubroeck et al., 2012). From the results it is proved that both Employee Performance is positively affected because of employee wellbeing, a sustainable HR dimension. (Chughtai et al.,2015), morality-based leadership is predominantly important because of employees' behaviours and attitudes, their creativity, well-being, organisational citizenship behaviour, job satisfaction, in-role performance. According to the study (Nazarian et al., 2017) the alliance of organisational culture and national culture with performance and organisational effectiveness. Further studies demonstrate that good leadership; EWB and Employee Performance positively connected to each other (Chen and Hou 2016).

Important aspects of Employee well-being

Apart from above mentioned aspects of EWB, there are some important aspects also which we need to discuss like work life balance, corporate culture, stress management etc. These are very important aspects which play pivotal role in someone's professional as well as personal life.

Work Life Balance (WLB) and EWB and Employee Performance

The concept of work life balance states that a person's both personal and professional life must be at par. It means there must be an equilibrium condition between personal and professional life. Now a days everywhere we see that all are burdened with professional work and don't even find sufficient time for their personal stuffs like child care, house hold activities, family time, health issues etc. The very concept of work life balance states that apart from executing the professional work a person must do his/ her personal work and must be able to maintain balance. Why it is important because by maintaining proper work life balance it helps in lessening stress, burnout, improves mental health. By setting boundaries, prioritizing tasks, and utilizing flexible schedules it can boost performance.

Though WLB is a very emerging topic and has significant importance also, still people are confused about it because of the over burdening jobs people are indulged in. Earlier EWB meant work family balance and it was mainly associated with working women because of handling child care responsibilities. So, this concept was very much gender biased as it was commonly perceived that women should be doing all child care responsibilities. And this perception was not wrong even because we used to live in such a society where child care duties, house hold chores are always linked to females.

Then later it was recognized that it's no more gender biased and all can come in this sphere. Men are also equally responsible for involving in family well-being and childcare Evans et al. (2013).

Then it was considered as people also have a self-life too. They must retain some time for own self Grisslich et al. (2012). So, the concept of 8+8+8 rule came into existence which denotes the equal time division of a person, 8 hours of work, 8 hours of sleep and 8 hours for own self.

Some research scholars find WLB as the reconciliation of work and private life and some advocate it for the integration of work and private life (Abendroth & Dulk, 2011) and there must be as an equal division of time between both. Some other scholars define it as the level of gratification one feels if he /she achieves harmony in all spheres of life. So, they define WLB as one must get satisfaction if he/she willingly engages in work. There are mainly 3 aspects of work-life balance: time balance, participation balance, and satisfaction balance (Oosthuizen et al., 2016).

Different research works have conducted to know the impact of organisational, individual, external, and demographic factors on work – life balance (Abendroth & Dulk, 2011; Poulouse & Sudarsan, 2017). These factors generate healthy effect on WLB by lessening work stress (Bell et al., 2012; Humayon et al., 2018), transformational leadership (Munir et al. 2012), a healthy work environment (Nordenmark et al., 2012), agile work practices, and the work autonomy (Hayman, 2010; Emre & Spiegeleare, 2019), partner support (Abendroth & Dulk, 2011), and individual efforts to balance out well-being (Zheng et al., 2016).

Its seems like it's an intricate process that both the professional work and personal work are both harmonized and it depends upon of an individual's personal life and work situation (Eurofound, Dublin, 2012). Several positive aspects are involved with positive WLB such as lower turnover, Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB), higher work engagement, increased productivity and organisational commitment (Kim, 2014), as well as job satisfaction, life and employee wellbeing (Taşdelen-Karckay & Bakalım, 2017).

On the other side if WLB is not properly managed or employees are unable to separate family and job roles, mental withdrawal from work, non-conducive or toxic work environment have gloomy impact on family life, job life, non-satisfaction at work etc (Nordenmark et al., 2012; Kalliath et al., 2017; Skurak et al., 2018). And all these negative impacts create job stress, anxiety, tension etc (Taşdelen-Karckay & Bakalım, 2017). So, we can see that WLB is a very significant driver of EWB (Beauregard, 2011; Bentley et al., 2016; Taşdelen-Karckay & Bakalım, 2017), having merits and demerits (Beauregard, 2011; Bentley et al., 2016; Taşdelen-Karckay & Bakalım, 2017).

Work culture, Stress Management and EWB and Employee Performance

The concept of work culture means the collecting feelings value, behaviour within an organization which defines the way employees should work and interact with each other. A healthy constructive work environment is always employee friendly by nature and so its employees. It emphasizes EWB, belief, collaboration and trust, open communication, listening to its employees even-if it's a very small idea, supportive leadership, giving autonomy to the employees, work life balance, recognition and reward. All these factors lead to high productivity, loyalty, commitment, OCB etc. On the contrary a negative or poor work culture which is characterized by absence of all these

above-mentioned features like non-supporting environment, no trust, poor leadership, no autonomy, not giving values to the ideas etc. All these factors of work culture may lead to low productivity, high stress, and high employee turnover.

The significance of work culture is as follows:

Employee Retention: A healthy work culture constructive which directly relates to job satisfaction and employee retention. It's very important to retain good talented employees in the organization. It's rightly said that hiring talent is not tough, but to retain is. Because if the work culture is good and employees stay there for a long tenure its itself a positive sign about the company. Ultimately low employee turnover ratio enhances the brand image. And on the other way if the work culture is not good, and having high employee turnover ratio it also enhances brand image of the company but in a negative way. So, it's very crucial to have good employee retention.

Employee Performance: A strong corporate culture which enhances work efficiency, boosts productivity, and helps achieve organizational goals. Employee performance always been a part of corporate culture. EP and culture are also directly related to each other. If the work culture is healthy and positive its certainly employees will perform better and better. And conversely if work culture is not good enough, employee's performance will also not be good.

Organization Reputation: Reputation, brand image has always been considered as the assets of any company. Sound work culture nourishes brand name in a positive way and it can entice good talent into the system effortlessly.

All these 3 factors are interrelated to each other. Employee retention is related to employee performance and ultimately leads to organization performance and reputation.

One more important factor of WLB and EWB is Work culture or corporate culture that exist in the workplace (Santos et al., 2013). Every employee perceives his/her work place having some particular culture without which they cannot exist as culture is the very reason of our existence. It binds all of us in a social bond and helps us to stay unitedly (Ismail et al., 2018). People feel free to speak their own mind and express their feelings or issues if any to others. Opening up with colleagues, expressing views, ideas, sharing thoughts are the healthy signs of a corporate culture. And if these types work culture exists, there will be certainly a family-friendly culture which enhances an atmosphere of tolerance, brotherhood, humanity, being supported etc (Santos et al., 2013) which are very significant in enhancing personal and organizational growth.

According to Bailyn (1997) has defined three characteristics of such work culture

- Temporal flexibility
- Operational flexibility
- Supportive supervision.

Temporal flexibility

Temporal flexibility is the system of a chance given to the employee having their own view point and tune the work schedule accordingly. Maximum number of employees believe on this system because it gives employees a sense of freedom and autonomy. A sense of autonomy in the workplace is a very moral boost for some employees especially top-ranking executives who utilise their strong cognitive power in decision making. Planning flexibility improves employees' work productivity, minimizes work related stress, absenteeism efficiency (Hoeven & Zoonen, 2015; Clarke & Holdsworth, 2017). It also gives relaxation to female employees having enormous house hold responsibilities and to working mothers like ample vacation and flexible scheduling policies which give them job satisfaction and well-being (Moen et al., 2016).

Operational flexibility

It is the system of giving autonomy or freedom to the employees in the workplace and control over working conditions. An atmosphere of trust must be their employees can take decision without feeling of surveillance and restriction (Bailyn, 1997). That is why independent and self-employed people are more engaged and satisfied with their work if there are no fatigue and stress (Boxall & Macky, 2014). They don't have to answerable to others as they are self-sufficient and this self-sufficiency is one of the important aspects of EWB, motivation and engagement (Olesen et al., 2015). Organizations where operational flexibility exists, the employees are more productive, satisfied. This flexibility gives them scope to manage both job and family issues as there is no disputes between family and job (Rastogi et al., 2016).

Supportive Supervision

In the system of supportive supervision, employees having family responsibilities can get direct support and helping hand from their supervisor (Bailyn, 1997). Here exists the concept of healthy communication between employees and their managers. Different aspects of EWB exist like mutual support, honesty. And this supportive supervision can reduce job stress, role conflict, and it improves loyalty towards the organization etc (Matthews et al., 2014).

According to (Abendroth & Dulk,2011), disclosed the impact of family-friendly work culture on both family and work. Every human being has both the duties to perform, job and family as both are important for survival. So, a person needs to make a balance in between the two. The results of different studies show that job satisfaction (Bentley et al., 2016), always dependent upon love caring of family members. The moral support that they provide to the person which becomes a pivotal reason for loyalty towards the company and generally do not think of leaving their jobs (Ahmad & Omar, 2010; Singh et al., 2018). Organizations who support family policy experience low job stress, good WLB (Ni & Wang, 2015; Caesens et al., 2017; Humayon et al., 2018). It is also seen that not only family members support, but support from line managers in the organizations also linked to job satisfaction (Beauregard, 2011).

Stress Management:

When in any job the requirements surpass a person's reach like abilities, needs and resources, it creates a detrimental impact on both physical and emotional, it's called the job stress. Generally, it occurs from intensive workload, target achievement, feeling of job insecurity etc. And the impact of stress is very fatal and deadly such as physical, mental, psychological, emotional breakdown, diminished efficiency. So, it's very important to manage the stress as it hampers the employee performance.

Today we all are living in an atmosphere where we can never get rid of or completely eradicate stress. Human life is full of stress and tension. Despite knowing the fact everybody is in stress. But what is more crucial how reduce or manage the stress. Stress management can be understood as the managing the stress. It's the application of techniques, strategies, and lifestyle changes which are chalked out to help people in order to manage, cope-up with their stress. So, stress management techniques focus on adapting stress, maintaining health both physical and mental in order to be prevented from its negative impact.

In the opinion of Folksman (1994), the pressing priority is stress management. A person may use every possible way not to be in stress, but every time dragged into stress. But instead of avoiding it one must learn how to manage or reduce the stress properly.

Research work

Our research work aims to learn about different EWB activities and the impact on employee performance. In order to carry out our research work we have taken 205 no. of IT sector professionals as our sample. We have prepared the questionnaire based on different factors of EWB and collected the responses through an on-line survey.

Objectives of the study:

1. To understand whether IT sectors are executing any employee well-being activities as a new dimension of Sustainable HRM.
2. To establish the connection between employee well-being and Employee Performance.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of the study is different IT sector professional based all over India.

Research Methodology:

Empirical data were collected from professionals from IT sector in India. The target group were consists of 205 no of employees. In the survey the researchers have tried to establish the connection between Employee Performance with employee well-being practice.

- Both Primary and secondary data were collected.
- Sample size for primary data: 205

- Sampling method: Convenient Sampling through Google form
- Secondary source of Data was from different website and company's annual reports.

Limitations of the study:

In our study we did face certain limitations.

- The study was limited in a way that in-depth investigation could not be completed within a cutoff time period.
- The research is conducted with a limited no. of responses due to work from home concept.

Data Analysis

Feature Selection

- Overall, Job Satisfaction (target variable)
- Employee Happiness
- Stress Level
- Retention Intention
- Productivity

Before feature selection

Figure:1

Result and Discussion:

The correlation heatmap illustrates the relationships among different workplace, health, and personal well-being factors. Each square in the heatmap represents the correlation between two variables, while the colors indicate the strength and direction of the relationship. Warmer colors such as yellow and green represent positive correlations, meaning that the variables tend to increase together, whereas cooler colors such as blue and purple represent negative correlations, indicating that as one variable increases, the other tends to decrease. The diagonal line of bright yellow squares represents perfect correlations of each variable with itself, which always equals 1.

One of the strongest positive relationships shown in the heatmap is between **“happy at work”** and **“co-workers are friendly and supportive.”** It indicates that employees feel happier at workplace those who get a supportive and friendly colleagues.

The interpretation reflects social support, team work and communication contributes to enjoyable workplace. There exists a correlation between "positive place to work" and workplace satisfaction,

emphasizing that company culture and environment have a remarkable influence on employee satisfaction.

Further, it depicts certain positive links among well-being variables such as “mental health issues” experiences a positive relationship with having a “positive place to work” and sustaining a “nutritionally balanced lunch,” signifying that supportive work conditions and healthier eating habits may be associated with enhanced mental well-being. In a similar way, “posture and ergonomics” is temperately positively connected to the feeling that “the things you do in your life are worthwhile,” which suggests that better physical comfort and ergonomic practices may be related to a greater sense of purpose and life satisfaction.

It also reflects that there is a negative correlation between "happy at work" and "search employment opportunities," which states that contented workers are typically less inclined to look for work elsewhere. Similarly, "things you do in your life are worthwhile" and "co-workers are friendly and supportive" are negatively correlated. It indicates an inverse relationship between these parameters within the dataset, despite the fact that the relationship is not very strong.

Finally, it concludes that various aspects of work life, personal health, and overall life satisfaction are interlinked. It shows that employees who get supportive relationships and a healthy work environment are usually more satisfied, while those who feel unhappy in their jobs are more likely to reflect changing employment.

Figure:2

Result and Discussion:

It depicts a comparative representation of employee survey results across five key dimensions of workplace experience and work-life balance. The data suggests that employees generally hold a positive view of their workplace, especially regarding relationships and flexibility.

The indicators related to work-life balance show slightly more fluctuation. Both Optimal work-life balance and Balance workload with family follow a comparable pattern, with most values grouped closely together but each containing one low outlier. This suggests that although the majority of employees report a reasonable balance only a small portion are away from this.

Finally, the visualization reflects an overall positive workplace atmosphere, especially in terms of flexibility and colleague relations. This also signifies a few isolated concerns and some variability in work-life balance, suggesting that certain areas could be improvised to achieve a more consistent employee experience.

Figure:3

Result and Discussion:

The findings reveals that workplace plays a significant role in influencing employee well-being and overall satisfaction. It states that Posture and Ergonomics along with Mental Health Issues are highly recommended predictors whereas factors such as Happy at work, Reasonable workload, and Optimal work-life balance show a moderate level of impact. Meanwhile, Flexible hours and Adequate office equipment represents relatively minimal influence on the overall outcome.

These suggest that organizations should play greater emphasis on supporting employees' physical health and mental well-being, rather than focusing primarily on administrative benefits like flexible working arrangements.

Figure:4

Result and Discussion:

The results indicate that the most important positive contributors are having a balanced lunch, actively looking for new job opportunities, and experiencing good overall life or work-life satisfaction.

In contrast, the main negative influences include taking breaks away from the computer, which has the strongest negative effect, along with a lower sense of purpose, an unsupportive or poor work environment, and reduced coworker or organizational support. Flexible working hours show little to no noticeable effect on the outcome.

Overall, healthy daily habits and active engagement in career development are linked with better results, while weaker workplace conditions and some unexpected behaviour patterns are associated with poorer outcomes.

Figure:5

Result and Discussion:

The boxplot chart provides a comparative overview of response distributions across 11 workplace and quality-of-life survey metrics, highlighting medians, spread, variability, and potential outliers on a 0–5 scale.

In general, most responses are concentrated between 0 and 2, which indicates relatively low to moderate scores across several factors of employee well-being. It reflects that Happy at work variable reflects a moderate level of satisfaction whereas Positive place to work shows a wide range, suggesting that employees have mixed and varied opinions about their workplace environment.

The variable Personal workload harming productivity stands out and reflects that some respondents experience very high workload pressure that affects productivity whereas Posture and ergonomics follows a more balanced pattern. The statement Things you do in life is highly concentrated showing strong agreement among most participants.

Finally, the chart reflects moderate employee satisfaction levels, fairly consistent patterns across many measures, but also indicates concerns such as workload pressure, differing views on workplace positivity, and occasional extreme responses.

After Feature selection

Figure:6

Result and Discussion:

It shows how various workplace factors are associated with employee happiness. The key results are summarized below:

- The strongest factor influencing happiness is supportive colleagues, with a correlation of 0.53 with “happy at work,” showing that good team relationships are a major contributor to employee satisfaction.
- Work-life balance has a moderate positive linkage with happiness (0.30) and also reflects a slight link with friendly interactions among coworkers.
- Flexible working hours have almost no relationship with work-life balance, indicating that flexibility on its own does not significantly reduce work-related stress.
- Flexibility also reflects a slight negative associations with coworker support (-0.14) and happiness (-0.07), which may indicate that reduced direct interaction may slightly impact team bonding and overall workplace satisfaction.

Figure:7

Result and Discussion:

It reflects how various workplace and well-being variables are interlinked to a target outcome using correlation values. Correlation describes both the direction and strength of relationships between variables.

The strongest positive relationship is seen in “co-workers are friendly and supportive,” which depicts a strong linkage among supportive team interactions and higher target values, emphasizing the importance of positive workplace relationships and collaboration.

A weak positive association is visualized for “personal workload is harming my productivity.” Similarly, “eat a nutritionally balanced lunch” reflects a very small positive correlation, implying only a limited connection with the variable.

Several features, including “time off for personal reasons,” “mental health issues,” “reasonable workload,” and “positive place to work,” have correlation values close to zero which indicates that they do not have a strong relationship.

It demonstrates that workplace and personal factors influence the target variable in different ways. Strong coworker support appears to be the most important positive factor, as compared to job-seeking behavior and certain perception-based measures.

Key findings include:

- **Generally positive workplace sentiment:** Most employees report being **happy at work**, with responses clustering around moderate-to-high scores.
- **Mixed job retention intentions:** Responses for **searching employment opportunities** are polarized, suggesting one group is actively considering leaving while another is not.
- **Workload concerns are significant:** The **reasonable workload** metric is heavily skewed toward low scores, indicating many employees feel overworked.
- **Strong peer relationships:** Employees overwhelmingly agree that **co-workers are friendly and supportive**, showing a consistently positive social environment.
- **Mental health concerns are widespread:** The **mental health issues** distribution is broad and evenly spread, implying concerns exist across many employees rather than within a small subgroup.
- **Perception of workplace positivity is divided:** The **positive place to work** metric is strongly bimodal, reflecting a split between highly satisfied and dissatisfied employees.
- **Low personal time-off usage:** Most employees report taking little to no **time off for personal reasons**, suggesting possible work pressure or poor work-life balance.
- **Productivity impact varies:** While many employees say workload does not harm productivity, a noticeable minority experiences significant negative effects.
- **Nutrition habits are inconsistent:** Responses for **eating a nutritionally balanced lunch** are highly split, indicating contrasting lifestyle behaviors among employees.
- **Good ergonomic conditions:** Most respondents gave high scores for **posture and ergonomics**, indicating generally favorable physical work conditions.
- **Strong sense of purpose:** The metric “**things you do in life are worthwhile**” shows an overwhelming concentration around a single positive score, reflecting strong alignment or shared sentiment among employees.

Conclusion:

Employee happiness is influenced more by supportive team connections and a genuine balance in workload than by flexible working hours on their own. Seeing the above findings, it can be concluded that employee wellbeing is a major concern in IT sectors. A study which is done keeping in view the employee wellbeing and employee performance gives convincing facts about the

overall wellbeing, which can be managed by various factors like interpersonal relationships, less workload, mental health, personal time-off etc. There are substantial facts and figures in the above data analysis that lead to establish the connection between employee well-being and Employee Performance. In future the study can further be extended through the same pattern with different data set to establish the relationship of employee's wellbeing with employees connect. There is a huge requirement of such type of study in future to take care of employees' Emotional Intelligence in both goods and service sectors.

References:

1. Abendroth, A. K., & Den Dulk, L. (2011). Support for the work-life balance in Europe: The impact of state, workplace and family support on work-life balance satisfaction. *Work, Employment and Society*, 25(2), 234–256. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0950017011398892>
2. Ahmad, A., & Omar, Z. (2010). Perceived family-supportive work culture, affective commitment and turnover intention of employees. *Journal of American Science*, 6(12), 839–846.
3. Appelbaum, E. (2002). The impact of new forms of work organization on workers. In Murray, G., Belanger, J., Giles, A. and Lapointe, P.A. (eds), *Work Employment Relations in the High-Performance Workplace*. London: Continuum, pp. 120–148.
4. Bailyn, L. (1997). The impact of corporate culture on work-family integration. In S. Parasuraman & J. H. Greenhaus (Eds.), *Integrating work and family: Challenges and choices for a changing world* (pp. 209–219). Quorum Books.
5. Beauregard, T. A. (2011). Direct and indirect links between organizational work-home culture and employee well-being. *British Journal of Management*, 22(2), 218–237. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8551.2010.00723.x>
6. Becker, B. / Huselid, M. / Ulrich, D. (2001): *The HR scorecard: Linking people, strategy, and performance*. Harvard Business School Press.
7. Bell, S. A., Rajendran D., & Theiler, S. (2012). Job stress, wellbeing, work-life balance and work-life conflict among Australian academics. *Electronic Journal of Applied Psychology*, 8(1), 25–37. <https://doi.org/10.7790/ejap.v8i1.320>
8. Bentley, T. A., Teo, S. T. T., McLeod, L., Tan, F., Bosua, R., & Gloet, M. (2016). The role of organisational support in teleworker wellbeing: A socio-technical systems approach. *Applied Ergonomics*, 52, 207–215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2015.07.019>
9. Boehm, J. K., and Lyubomirsky, S. (2008). Does happiness promote career success? *J. Career Assess.* 16, 101–116. doi: 10.1177/1069072707308140

10. Boselie, P. / Dietz, G. / Boon, C. (2005). Commonalities and contradictions in research on human resource management and performance. In: *Human Resource Management Journal*, 15 (13): 67-94.
11. Boxall, P. and Macky, K. (2009). Research and theory on high-performance work systems: processing the highinvolvement stream. *Human Resource Management Journal*, **19**, pp. 3–23.
12. Boxall, P., & Macky, K. (2014). High-involvement work processes, work intensification and employee wellbeing. *Work, Employment and Society*, 28(6), 963–984. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017013512714>
13. Caesens, G., Stinglhamber, F., Demoulin, S., & De Wilde, M. (2017). Perceived organizational support and employees' well-being: The mediating role of organizational dehumanization. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 26(4), 527–540. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2017.1319817>
14. Chen, A. S. Y., & Hou, Y. H. (2016). The effects of ethical leadership, voice behavior and climates for innovation on creativity: A moderated mediation examination. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 27(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2015.10.007>
15. Cheng, J. W., Chang, S. C., Kuo, J. H., & Cheung, Y. H. (2014). Ethical leadership, work engagement, and voice behavior. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 114(5), 817–831.
16. Chughtai, A., Byrne, M., & Flood, B. (2015). Linking ethical leadership to employee well-being: The role of trust in supervisor. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 128(3), 653–663. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2126-7>
17. Clarke, S., & Holdsworth, L. (2017). *Flexibility in the workplace: Implications of flexible work arrangements for individuals, teams and organizations*. Alliance Manchester Business School. University of Manchester, Manchester, M13 9SS. <https://www.acas.org.uk/flexibility-in-the-workplace>
18. Combs, J., Liu, Y., Hall, A. and Ketchen, D. (2006). How much do high-performance work practices matter? A meta-analysis of their effects on organisational performance. *Personnel Psychology*, **59**, pp. 501–528.
19. Daniels, K. (2000): Measures of five aspects of affective well-being at work. In: *Human Relations*, 53 (2): 275-294.
20. Dewe, P., and Cooper, C. (2012). *Well-being and Work: Towards a Balanced Agenda*. Basingstoke: Palgrave MacMillan.

21. Dunham, J. (2001). Stress in the workplace: Past, present and future. *(No Title)*.
22. Emre, O., & De Spiegeleare, S. (2019). The role of work–life balance and autonomy in the relationship between commuting, employee commitment and well-being. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2019.1583270>
23. Eurofound. (2012). *Working time and WLB in a life course perspective*. Eurofound, Dublin. https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/sites/default/files/ef_publication/field_ef_document/ef1273en
24. Evans, A., Carney, J., & Wilkinson, M. (2013). Work–life balance for men: Counseling implications. *Journal of Counselling & Development*, 91(4), 436–441. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1556-6676.2013.00115.x>
25. Fishbein, M., and I. Ajzen, *Belief, attitude, intention, and behavior: An introduction to theory and research*, Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley, 1975.
26. Folksman, G.H. (1994). *Managing Stress Subjectivity and Power in the Workplace*. Thousand Oaks, cliff, sage Wharton A.S. and Brikson. R.I. 457.
27. Grisslich, P., Proske, A., & Körndle, H. (2012). Beyond work and life – what role does time for oneself play in work-life-balance? *Zeitschrift für Gesundheitspsychologie*, 20(4), 166–177. <https://doi.or.10.1026/0943-8149/a000076>
28. Guest, D. (1997). Human resource management and performance: a review and research agenda. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 8, pp. 263–276.
29. Hayman, J. (2010). Flexible work schedules and employee well-being. *New Zealand Journal of Employment Relations*, 35(2), 76–87. [http://www.nzjournal.org/NZJER35\(2\).pdf](http://www.nzjournal.org/NZJER35(2).pdf)
30. Hellgren, J., Sverke, M., and Näswall, K. (2008). “Changing work roles: new demands and challenges,” in *The Individual in the Changing Working Life*, eds K. Näswall, J. Hellgren, and M. Sverke (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press), 46–66.
31. Ter Hoeven, C. L., & Van Zoonen, W. (2015). Flexible work designs and employee well-being: Examining the effects of resources and demands. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 30(3), 237-255.
32. Holman, D. (2002): Employee wellbeing in call centres. In: *Human Resource Management Journal*, 12 (4): 35-50.

33. Humayon, A. A., Raza, S., Kaleem, N., Murtaza, G., Hussain, M. S., & Abbas, Z. (2018). Impact of supervision, working condition and university policy on work-life balance of university employees. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 7(1), 193–201. <https://european-science.com/eojnss/article/view/5253>
34. Huselid, M.A. (1995): The impact of human resource practices on turnover, productivity and corporate financial performance. In: *Academy of Management Journal* 38 (3): 635-670.
35. Ismail, M., Baki, N. U., & Omar, Z. (2018). The influence of organizational culture and organizational justice on group cohesion as perceived by merger and acquisition employees. *Organizations & Markets in Emerging Economies*, 9(2), 233–250. <https://doi.org/10.15388/omee.2018.10.00012>
36. Keyes, C. L. M., and Grzywacz, J. G. (2005). Health as a complete state: the added value in work performance and healthcare costs. *J. Occup. Environ. Med.* 47,523–532. doi: 10.1097/01.jom.0000161737.21198.3a
37. Legge, K. (1995). *Human Resource Management: Rhetorics and Realities*. Basingstoke: Macmillan.
38. Lyubomirsky, S., King, L., and Diener, E. (2005). The benefits of frequent positive affect: does happiness lead to success? *Psychol. Bull.* 131, 803–855. doi: 10.1037/0033-2909.131.6.803
39. Kalliath, P., Kalliath, T., & Chan, C. (2017). Work–family conflict, family satisfaction and employee well-being: A comparative study of Australian and Indian social workers. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 27(3), 366–381. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12143>
40. Kim, H. K. (2014). Work-life balance and employees' performance: The mediating role of affective commitment. *Global Business and Management Research*, 6(1), 37–51. https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Work-Life-Balance-and-Employees%27-Performance%3A-The-Kim/b2a0018b12b37416_dd8418ef1342bbb34dde02a0
41. Matthews, R. A., Mills, M. J., Trout, R. C., & English, L. (2014). Family-supportive supervisor behaviors, work engagement, and subjective well-being: A contextually dependent mediated process. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 19(2), 168–181. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0036012>
42. McDonough, P. (2000): Job insecurity and health. In: *International Journal of Health Services*, 30: 453- 476.

43. Moen, P., Kelly, E. L., Fan, W., Lee, S. R., Almeida, D., Kossek, E. E., & Buxton, O. M. (2016). Does a flexibility/support organizational initiative improve high-tech employees' well-being? Evidence from the work, family, and health network. *American Sociological Review*, 81(1), 134–164. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0003122415622391>
44. Munir, F., Nielsen, K., Garde, A. H., Albertsen, K., & Carneiro, I. G. (2012). Mediating the effects of work–life conflict between transformational leadership and health-care workers' job satisfaction and psychological wellbeing. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 20(4), 512–521. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2834.2011.01308.x>
45. Nazarian, A., Atkinson, P., & Foroudi, P. (2017). Influence of national culture and balanced organizational culture on the hotel industry's performance. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 63, 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2017.01.003>
46. Nishii, L. and Wright, P. (2008). Variability within organizations: implications for strategic human resource management. In Smith, D.B. (ed.), *The People Make the Place: Dynamic Linkages between Individuals and Organizations*. New York: Taylor & Francis, pp. 225–248.
47. Ni, C., & Wang, Y. (2015). The impact of perceived organizational support and core self-evaluation on employee's psychological well-being. *Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies*, 3(2), 73–81. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jhrss.2015.32011>
48. Nordenmark, M., Vinberg, S., & Strandh, M. (2012). Job control and demands, work-life balance and wellbeing among self-employed men and women in Europe. *Vulnerable Groups & Inclusion*, 3(1), 18896. <https://doi.org/10.3402/vgi.v3i0.18896>
49. Olesen, M. H., Thomsen, D. K., & O'Toole, M. S. (2015). Subjective well-being: Above neuroticism and extraversion, autonomy motivation matters. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 77, 45–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2014.12.033>
50. Oosthuizen, R. M., Coetzee, M., & Munro, Z. (2016). Work-life balance, job satisfaction and turnover intention amongst information technology employees. *Southern African Business Review*, 20(1), 446–467. <https://doi.org/10.25159/1998-8125/6059>
51. Poulouse, S., & Sudarsan, N. (2017). Assessing the influence of work-life balance dimensions among nurses in the healthcare sector. *Journal of Management Development*, 36(3), 427–437. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMD-12-2015-0188>

52. Ramsay, H., Scholarios, D. and Harley, B. (2000). Employees of high-performance work systems: testing inside the black box. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, **38**, pp. 501–531.
53. Rastogi, M., Rangnekar, S., & Rastogi, R. (2016). Flexibility as a predictor of work–family enrichment. *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, *17*(1), 5–14.
54. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40171-015-0108-y>
55. Ryff, C.D / Keyes, C.L.M. (1995): The structure of psychological well-being revised. In: *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *69*: 719-727.
56. Santos, J., Goncalves, G., & Gomes, A. (2013). Organizational culture and subjective and work wellbeing. The case of employees of Portuguese universities. *Journal of Spatial and Organizational Dynamics*, *1*(3), 153–161. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/ris/jspord/0009.html>
57. Sarwar, H., Ishaq, M. I., Amin, A., & Ahmed, R. (2020). Ethical leadership, work engagement, employees' well-being, and performance: a cross-cultural comparison. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, *28*(12), 2008-2026. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1788039>
58. Schaubroeck, J. M., Hannah, S. T., Avolio, B. J., Kozlowski, S. W. J., Lord, R. G., Treviño, L. K., Dimotakis, N., & Peng, A. C. (2012). Embedding ethical leadership within and across organization levels. *Academy of Management Journal*, *55*(5), 1053–1078. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2011.0064>
59. Singh, R., Zhang, Y., Wan, M., & Fouad, N. A. (2018). Why do women engineers leave the engineering profession? The roles of work–family conflict, occupational commitment, and perceived organizational support. *Human Resource Management*, *57*(4), 901–914. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.21900>
60. Skurak, H., Malinen, S., Naswall, K., & Kuntz, J. C. (2018). Employee wellbeing: The role of psychological detachment on the relationship between engagement and work–life conflict. *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, *42*(1), 116–141. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143831X17750473>
61. Strauss, G., "Human relations – 1968 style," *Industrial Relations*, *7*, 262-276, 1968
62. Taşdelen-Karckay, A., & Bakalim, O. (2017). The mediating effect of work–life balance on the relationship between work–family conflict and life satisfaction. *Australian Journal of Career Development*, *26*(1), 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1038416216682954>

63. Vahtera, J. / Kivimäki, M. / Pentti, J. (1997): Effect of organisational downsizing on health of employees. In: *The Lancet*, 350: 1124-1128.
64. Warr, P. (1990): The measurement of well-being and other aspects of mental health. In: *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63: 193-210.
65. Zheng, C., Kashi, K., Fan, D., Molineux, J., & Ee, M. S. (2016). Impact of individual coping strategies and organisational work–life balance programmes on Australian employee well-being. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(5), 501–526. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2015.1020447>